

Tradeoffs in Computer Interaction Styles

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Abstract

System design involves a series of tradeoffs. The benefit of one design technique will impact the benefits of another. Developers must weigh the advantages and disadvantages of each approach in order to design a system most suitable for the end user. Studies have been performed to determine users' preferences for various system designs. In particular, studies have shown that menu selection and direct manipulation systems are favored by novices and intermediate computer users, while command language interaction is desired by experienced users. What performance characteristics or design attributes attracted the users to the interaction style? What performance characteristics are users willing to tradeoff in order to obtain their desired system? Multiattribute Utility Analysis (MAUA) is presented to illustrate how formal approaches to decision making can be used to select alternatives for computer interaction styles.

Keywords: interaction styles; novice, intermediate, and experienced computer users; multiattribute utility analysis; tradeoffs.

1. Introduction

Every business, school, office, and practically every home is equipped with a computer---personal computer (PC), laptop, Macintosh, workstation, etc. Industry analysts report that 31% of U.S. households alone own microcomputers and expect the numbers to increase to 50% by the year 1997 [15]. Computers are being utilized to store, analyze, manipulate, display, and transfer data. What used to require hours of manual calculations, now takes a matter of seconds. For many people, computers have become a necessity.

The computer industry draws a conglomerate number of users: novice users, intermediate users, and experienced users. A novice user can be defined as a first time, casual, inexperienced computer user. Intermediate

users can be defined as regular computer users, yet are not considered programmers. They are familiar with some of the computer jargon and know how to operate most computer systems. Experienced users, on the other hand, can be categorized as programmers, system designers, analysts, and computer specialists. It should be noted, however, that although there are various levels of computer users, these same users whether novice, intermediate, or experienced are normally experts in the tasks for which the computer systems have been developed.

With these types of users in mind, it is essential for computer systems to be designed to address the computer capabilities of the end user. Many powerful applications have been developed but are unsuccessful because they lack usability and fail to meet the user's computer capabilities. "A usable system is not only user friendly but is also normal to use. A system that is normal to use is tailored to the particular tasks, personal characteristics, and operating environment of the people using it. It may not necessarily be the easiest of systems to use--because the tasks for which it is used may not be easy--but it does allow the people using it to accomplish their work without making the system's presence known" [20].

How can a system be designed that is not intimidating to a person with little or no computer background yet not so 'user friendly' that it lacks functionality and cripples the experienced and intermediate user? Research has found that flexible system designs attract the intermediate and experienced users [17], [24], [28]; whereas, systems providing adequate feedback or informative messages draw the novice user [9], [22]. Additionally, in his research on interaction styles, Shneiderman [24] discovers that menu selection is most beneficial to the novice and/or intermediate users. This style may not be favored by experienced users since it may slow down their performance. Command language, on the other hand, provides the flexibility desired by experienced users. For the novice user, this interaction style may be disfavored

due to complexity and lack of error message feedback [24]. Direct manipulation is appealing to both the novice and intermediate users, and if carefully designed can be beneficial to the experienced user [24].

The above studies utilized surveys/questionnaires and controlled experiments to obtain results on user preferences. This paper presents Multiattribute Utility Analysis (MAUA) as an illustration of how formal decision making methods can be used identify user preferences for system design. Specifically, MAUA will be used to ascertain the tradeoffs users are willing to make when faced with three alternative interaction styles: menu selection, command language, and direct manipulation.

2. Multiattribute utility analysis

“Design is a series of tradeoffs. Assistance for one stage is apt to interfere with another. Any single design technique is apt to have its virtues along one dimension compensated by deficiencies along another. Each technique provides a set of tradeoffs. Add extra help for the unskilled user and you run the risk of frustrating the experienced user. Make the display screen larger and some tasks get better, but others get more confused. Display more information, and the time to paint the display goes up, the memory requirements goes up, programs become larger, bulkier, slower. It is well known that different tasks and classes of users have different needs and requirements”[14].

Multiattribute Utility Analysis (MAUA) is used to compare the overall value of different alternatives as a function of several performance characteristics [27]. It involves (1) identifying the alternatives to be compared and the decision makers, (2) clarifying the goals and objectives, (3) identifying performance characteristics or attributes, (4) defining attribute ranges, (5) determining single attribute utility functions (6) determining scaling constants, (7) ranking the alternatives, and (8) performing sensitivity analysis to see how changes in levels of performance characteristics or preferences affects the results. Each of these steps is explained in the sections that follow.

2.1 Identify alternatives and the decision makers

The decision analysis begins with the identification of alternatives. These are the choices that are ranked in order to make the decision. Some examples of alternatives are: choosing between three universities, choosing among 4 job offers, etc. Next, the persons responsible for evaluating the alternatives are identified. These people evaluate the design alternatives “in a way

that integrates all aspects of their overall desirability” [27].

2.2 Identify goals and objectives

Goals and objectives are what influence the desirability of the alternatives. A goals hierarchy is constructed to aid in the organization of the objectives. A goals hierarchy is a tree-like diagram that begins with the general goals at the top of the tree. These general goals are broken down into more specific goals until the objectives are specific enough to measure.

2.3 Determine performance characteristics

Performance characteristics are functional performance requirements used to rank the alternatives. To prevent bias toward or against any particular design, the design attributes must capture advantages and disadvantages for each alternative design [27]. Information is collected from the decision maker and from technical literature, conference proceedings, and journals. After the literature review, a preliminary list of performance characteristics is developed. Characteristics that are design requirements, have no significant effect on the overall design, and are convertible to a common metric are identified and eliminated [27]. The remaining performance characteristics or attributes are the ones to be considered in the analysis.

2.4 Define attribute ranges

Decision makers are asked to give a range of values (best to worst) for each attribute. This range denotes the values they are willing to accept for an attribute. For example, if the attribute were price in purchasing a house, the decision maker’s range would be \$80,000 to \$110,000. The decision maker expects to pay no less than \$80,000 and no more than \$110,000.

2.5 Determine single attribute utility functions

Because the attributes are defined in different units and scales, they cannot be combined into an overall score. It is therefore necessary to convert each attribute to a common scale or utility so that they can be combined. Utility is a desirability measure defined within the range of 0 and 1, where a utility of 0 is least preferred and a utility of 1 is most preferred. To obtain the single attribute utility function for each attribute, the decision maker is asked to consider two design alternatives that are the same in all attributes except one,

x_i . For one design, it is known for certain that the performance level of attribute x_i is some value x . For the other design, the performance level is uncertain. The decision maker must specify his or her preference for the certainty or the lottery.

Figure 1 illustrates a lottery question to assess the single attribute utility function $U_i(x_i)$ for memory requirements for a computer application. The lottery shows a probability p of 70% that the requirements will be 1 megabyte (MB) and a probability $(1-p)$ of 30% that the requirements will be 4 megabytes. As the certain memory attribute value changes, a preference for the certainty or the lottery is specified. When the decision maker reaches the point where he or she is indifferent between the certainty and the lottery, the certainty equivalent is determined using the equation below.

$$U_i(x_i) = pU_i(x_{ib}) + (1-p)U_i(x_{iw})$$

$$U_i(x_i) = p(1) + (1-p)(0)$$

$$U_i(x_i) = p$$

where x_{ib} and x_{iw} are the best and worst values of attribute levels, respectively. The value that's placed on the certainty equivalent is a point on the single attribute utility function. The questioning continues for another probability p . The reader is referred to section 3.4 for an example of how a utility function is plotted.

Figure 1: Lottery Question to Assess Single Attribute Utility Function $U_i(x_i)$ for Memory Requirements

2.6 Determine Scaling Constants

Once a single attribute utility function (SUF) has been defined for each attribute, the next step is to combine the SUFs into an overall utility for each alternative. The formula used to combine the SUF utilities is called the Multiattribute Utility Function (MUF). "A MUF takes a set of levels on the [attributes] and combines them to arrive at a single number representing the relative desirability of an alternative, called the alternative's overall utility. The alternative

with the highest overall utility is the most preferred" [11].

The equation 1 is the MUF and used in the decision analysis. $U_i(x_i)$ represents the assessed single attribute utility function which is the nonlinearity of preference over the acceptable attribute range, and k_i is the assessed single attribute scaling constant representing the tradeoff that the decision maker is willing to make between attributes [27]. For derivations of equation 1, the reader is referred to Thurston [27] and de Neufville [6].

$$U(X) = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i U_i(x_i) \quad (1)$$

The value of k_i is equal to the utility where x_i is at its best level, x_{ib} , and the other attributes are at their worst levels, i.e. $U(x_{1w}, \dots, x_{ib}, \dots, x_{nw}) = k_i$. When all attributes are at their best, $U(X_b) = 1$. When they are all at their worst, $U(X_w) = 0$. The value of k_i is therefore determined by

$$U(x_{1w}, \dots, x_{ib}, \dots, x_{nw}) = pU(X_b) + (1-p)U(X_w)$$

$$U(x_{1w}, \dots, x_{ib}, \dots, x_{nw}) = p(1) + (1-p)(0)$$

$$U(x_{1w}, \dots, x_{ib}, \dots, x_{nw}) = p \quad (2)$$

where $k_i = p$.

To find k_i , the decision maker is asked to specify his or her preference for a certainty or a lottery at various values of p . The value of p where the decision maker is indifferent between the certainty and the lottery is the k_i . Figure 2 illustrates a lottery to find k_i .

Figure 2: Lottery Question to Assess Scaling Constant k_i for Memory Requirements

2.7 Rank alternatives

The overall utility of each alternative is calculated using equation (1). This number represents the

alternative's relative desirability. The alternative with the highest overall utility is the most preferred.

2.8 Perform sensitivity analysis

Knowing the ranking of alternatives is not enough to indicate how much better one alternative is than another. What becomes important is how lower ranking alternatives should be improved to become competitive with higher ranking alternatives. This is accomplished through sensitivity analysis, where attribute levels are varied in order to determine (1) the effects on the overall utility for each alternative and (2) the trade-offs between attributes decision makers are willing to make to improve on the alternative.

3. Example

3.1 Alternatives, decision makers, and performance characteristics

The decision is to make a choice among three interaction styles for system applications: menu selection, command language, and direct manipulation. The decision makers surveyed were a novice, intermediate, and experienced computer user. Table 1 is a preliminary list of all the performance characteristics obtained from various books, journals, and computer magazines.

Interface and User Considerations	Hardware Considerations
Accuracy	Development cost
Amount of screen information	Memory requirements
Ease of use	Hardware requirements
Error prevention	Programming time
Display rate	
Flexibility	
Feedback:	
Informative messages	
System prompts	
Mode of Input	
Speed	
Training requirements	
'Undo' facility	
User memorization	
User satisfaction	

Table 1: Preliminary List of Performance Characteristics

Characteristics that were design requirements, had no significant effect on the overall design, and were convertible to a common metric were identified and eliminated. The most relevant characteristics then included: (1) flexibility, (2) ease of use, (3) feedback, (4) development cost, (5) training requirements, (6) user memorization, (7) programming time, (8) memory requirements, (9) 'undo' facility, (10) system prompts, and (11) informative error messages.

A goals hierarchy (figure 3) was developed to organize the eleven (11) characteristics and identify the 'measurable' ones. The attributes found at the lowest level of the hierarchy were used in the analysis.

Undo facility - This refers to a system allowing users to correct typing mistakes, cancel an operation, or backspace to previous menus in a system. For example, in the word processor Microsoft Word® version 6.0, users can backspace to delete characters and are able to undo as many as 100 actions. This attribute is measured by the number of times a user can undo an operation.

Training requirements - This attribute refers to the training time required to learn a given system. The unit of measurement is days.

User memorization - In some applications, users must know the system commands in order to use it. This attribute measures the amount of commands the users must know or memorize to use the application. The unit of measurement is percent (%).

System prompts - This characteristic refers to how often the system 'prompts' or assists the user through the system. The unit of measurement is percent (%).

Informative error messages - Often times when users make an unpermissible mistake, e.g. press the wrong key or entered invalid data, the system responds by putting an error message on the screen. Some times the message is detailed, e.g. WRONG DATA ENTRY FORMAT--SEPARATE EACH ENTRY WITH A SPACE. In other instances, the error message may consist of a computer code error, e.g. ERROR-9004. This attribute therefore measures the level of detail within an error message. It is measured on a scale of 1-5, where 1 denotes a preference for detailed error messages, 3 for short messages, and 5 for computer coded messages.

Programming time - This attribute refers to the time to program a system. This can also be described to novices or non-programmers as the amount of time they are willing to wait for a system application to be developed before using it. The unit of measurement is days.

Memory requirements - This attribute refers to the amount of computer memory an application requires. For novices or non-programmers, this attribute can be viewed as the more memory an application requires, the

more it will cost. The unit of measurement is megabytes (MB).

3.2 Goals and objectives

Figure 3 illustrates the goals hierarchy used to perform the analysis. The lowest level of each branch constitutes the 'measurable' attributes.

Figure 3: Goals Hierarchy for Interaction Style Selection

3.3 Attribute ranges

Programming time - The acceptable ranges in programming time for the experienced computer user and the novice user are 3 to 14 days and 3 to 7 days, respectively. This attribute was unimportant to the intermediate user.

Error messages - Both experienced and intermediate computer users were willing to accept a system that conveyed any level of error messages. The novice, on the other hand, would not accept a system unless all the error messages were detailed. This supports the research findings that novices require systems with adequate feedback and error messages [9], [22].

Training requirements - The novice and intermediate users are interested in a system with a learning time of 3 to 7 days and 2 to 7 days, respectively. The experienced user is willing to accept a system that has a training time no longer than 28 days, i.e. 4 weeks.

User memorization - The novice user will accept a system that requires no more than 25% of command memorization; whereas the experienced user will accept a system requiring up to 75%. On the other hand, the intermediate user preferred a system where most to all

commands were required to be learned. This supports the research of Shneiderman [24] where it was found that experienced and some intermediate users preferred command language interaction.

System prompts - The experienced user was willing to accept any range of system prompts. The novice preferred being prompted 90-100% of the time. The intermediate user disliked system prompts and preferred being prompted no more than 25% of the time.

Memory requirements - The novice and intermediate computer users were neutral regarding the memory requirements, and undo attributes. The experienced user preferred a system requiring no more than 4 MB of memory and allowing the user to undo as many as 10 operations. This strikes an interesting point: the more expertise one acquires in the area of computers, the more concerned he or she is about system hardware.

3.4 Single attribute utility functions and scaling constants

Figures 4 through 6 depict the decision makers' utility functions for training requirements. For example, in plotting the experienced computer user's utility function, lottery questions were asked (refer to section 2.5). The results indicated the users' certainty equivalents at 2, 3, and 4 weeks where the lotteries respectively consisted of 95%, 75% and 50% probabilities (p) of a week training period and 5%, 25%, and 50% probabilities (1-p) of a 4 week training period. The utilities were found using the equation below.

$$U_i(x_i) = pU_i(x_{ib}) + (1-p)U_i(x_{iw})$$

$$U_i(x_i) = p(1) + (1-p)(0)$$

$$U_i(x_i) = p$$

For example, the utility for the 2 week certainty equivalent is found as follows:

$$U(2 \text{ weeks}) = .95U(1 \text{ week}) + .05U(4 \text{ weeks})$$

$$U(2 \text{ weeks}) = .95(1) + .05(0)$$

$$U(2 \text{ weeks}) = .95$$

This example represents the (2, .95) point in figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Single Attribute Utility Function for Experienced User's Training Requirements

Figure 5: Single Attribute Utility Function for Intermediate User's Training Requirements

Figure 6: Single Attribute Utility Function for Novice User's Training Requirements

This procedure was repeated for each attribute. Once the decision makers' SUFs were obtained, Logical Decisions™, a decision making program, was used to obtain the scaling constants (see Table 2). Please note that the scaling constants appear as percentages (0 to 100) rather than probabilities (0 to 1). From the table, it can be seen that the experienced user values system prompts, and both the novice and intermediate users value training time. In other words, each user will give up or tradeoff very little of these attributes for other attributes (see section 3.6).

Decision Maker	Attribute	Scaling Constant (k)
Experienced User	Training	8.6
	User Memorization	8.6
	System Prompts	45.1
	Informative Error Messages	12.8
	Programming Time	12.3
	Memory Requirements	4.1
Intermediate User	Undo Facility	8.1
	Training	90.2
	System Prompts	4.5
	User Memorization	4.5
Novice User	Informative Error Messages	0.7
	Training	52.3
	System Prompts	11.9
	User Memorization	11.9
	Informative Error Messages	23.9

Table 2: Scaling Constants

3.5 Alternatives ranking

The decision makers estimated the performance levels for each alternative interaction style according to their relevant attribute ranges (Table 3). These estimations along with the scaling constants and single attribute utility functions are necessary to compute the overall utility of each alternative interaction style (equation 1).

Attributes	Alternative Interaction Styles		
	Menu	Command	Direct Manipulation
Experienced User:			
Training	1	2	2
User Memorization	0	100	0
System Prompts	100	0	100
Informative Error Messages	2	2	2
Programming	7	7	14
Memory Requirements	2	4	1
Undo Facility	1	0	1
Intermediate User:			
Training	2	3	2
User Memorization	95	100	100
System Prompts	100	5	0
Informative Error Messages	3	3	3
Novice User:			
Training	4	7	3
User Memorization	8	100	0
System Prompts	100	0	100
Informative Error Messages	2	4	3

Table 3: Estimated Attribute Levels

Each decision maker's overall utility for each alternative was computed. They appear in Tables 4

through 6. The alternative(s) with the highest utility is the preferred interaction style.

Interaction Style	Utility
Menu	.8368
Command	.1881
Direct Manipulation	.7591

Table 4: Experienced User's Overall Utilities

Interaction Style	Utility
Menu	.0841
Command	.9469
Direct Manipulation	.9983

Table 5: Intermediate User's Overall Utilities

Interaction Style	Utility
Menu	.7895
Command	0
Direct Manipulation	.7614

Table 6: Novice User's Overall Utilities

3.6 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis involves varying attribute levels in order to determine (1) its effects on the overall utility for each alternative and (2) the trade-offs between attributes decision makers are willing to make. The analysis focused on the latter. Logical Decisions™ was used to automate the tradeoff process. Each decision maker was asked to decide which of two hypothetical alternatives was preferred. These alternatives differed in their levels on two attributes; the other attributes were assumed to be at their best levels. Based on the decision maker's response, one of the alternative's attribute levels was systematically changed until the decision maker specified that the alternatives were equally preferred. This method is based on the idea that "equally preferred alternatives should have equal overall utilities" [11]. Once alternatives were specified as equally preferred, the decision maker was asked to assess two different attributes. This continued until all the attributes were included in the tradeoff process.

Results from the experienced user's tradeoffs indicated his willingness to tradeoff 90% of the 'undo' operations and 50% of training time for 100% system prompts. For more informative error messages, he was willing to tradeoff 20% of system prompts. Additionally, he would agree to increasing programming time for less memory requirements and user memorization.

Quite interestingly, the intermediate user was willing to increase training by a day and decrease error message details to have a system that required 100% memorization of the commands. Moreover, the user was willing to decrease the amount of system prompts (i.e. desired no prompts) for an additional day of training.

The novice user was willing to accept an increase in system training days for more system prompting and less memorization. The fact that he required/preferred system prompts at 100% verifies the finding that novices are drawn to systems that provide adequate feedback [9], [22].

4. Implications of Study

Formal decision making methods can be used to assist decision makers in choosing among design alternatives. In this study, MAUA was used to illustrate how formal approaches to decision making can be used to select alternatives for computer interaction. Results from the MAUA were validated by the findings of Shneiderman [22, 24], Lee and Paz [9], and others.

5. Conclusions

This research used a formal method, Multiattribute Utility Analysis (MAUA) to (1) determine a novice, intermediate, and experienced computer user's preference for three interaction styles: menu selection, command language, and direct manipulation and (2) to ascertain the tradeoffs users are willing to make between the interaction styles. Results from the MAUA indicate that the experienced user was willing to tradeoff 90% of system flexibility and 50% of training time for 100% system prompts. For more informative error messages, he was willing to tradeoff 20% of system prompts. Additionally, he would agree to increasing programming time for less memory requirements and user memorization.

On the other hand, the intermediate user was willing to increase training and decrease error message details to have a system that required 100% memorization of the commands. Moreover, the user was willing to decrease the amount of system prompts (i.e. desired no prompts) for an additional day of training. The novice user was willing to accept an increase in system training days for more system prompting and less memorization.

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